

DIRECTED Communication & Dissemination Strategy

Horizon Europe

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Report overview

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Executive summary

The DIRECTED Project is, by its nature, a highly collaborative project that from the outset will need the delivery of well thought out communications and dissemination actions that are tailored to the target audiences it wishes to address. The Project will use a range of techniques including detailed stakeholder engagement work using the Risk-Tandem Framework tool, production of training materials and training of trainers, tool demonstrations, as well as more uniform modern communication techniques such as mass media, website, social media, video, podcasts, webinars, blogs, published papers and conference dissemination. It will also target policy-maker communication and dissemination through developing policy briefs and specific policy-maker meetings and engagement.

Our goal is to deliver a comprehensive communications and dissemination programme that engages, informs and influences our target audiences and enables us to move towards our outcomes and in the longer term see the impacts we wish to make. Specifically, our target audiences include:

- 1) First and second responders
- 2) Regional and municipal civil authorities - including disaster management, planning authorities and cross regional municipalities
- 3) Physical and social scientific organisations - those who work in climate change, natural disaster sciences and damage and loss, governance and innovation
- 4) The general public - will be represented by municipalities

This strategy provides a broad outline of our goals and the communication and dissemination techniques we will use, as well as the Year 1 Communications and Dissemination plan that can be found at the end of the report.

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1. Introduction

This Communication and Dissemination Strategy sets the road map for the DIRECTED Project to succeed in reaching its stated goals and impacts and the communication and dissemination actions that will be required to support this. It will ensure that the correct acknowledgement of the European Union support of the Project can also be appreciated and how we will ensure that the wider understanding and use of the results achieved through the Project will be pursued.

1.1 Background of the Directed Project

The recent droughts and unprecedented floods in central Europe have illustrated our vulnerability to extreme weather events. Besides climate change as a driver of more frequent and intensifying weather extremes, demographic change and socio-economic development exacerbate severe impacts. International frameworks for Disaster Risk Reduction and Climate Change Adaptation (e.g. SENDAI framework, EU Strategy on adaptation to climate change) acknowledge the critical need for integrating risk governance, communication and operational mechanisms for coping with extreme climate events throughout the entire Disaster Risk Management cycle.

DIRECTED aspires to foster disaster-resilient European societies by expanding our capabilities to communicate, utilise and exchange state-of-the-art data, information and knowledge between different actors; boosting the integration, accessibility and interoperability of models; facilitating knowledge sharing; improving dialogue and cooperation encompassing all levels of actors based on enhanced community engagement and developing new governance and risk management strategies using a bottom-up, value-driven co-development approach. Key to supporting interoperability will be the establishment of the Data Fabric (Figure 2), an innovative, governed, cloud platform that enables secure, flexible, discovery and sharing of all structured and unstructured data. Thus, dissemination and communications are a core part of this project.

Central to DIRECTED are four Real World Labs that co-develop new governance, interoperability and knowledge production frameworks and demonstrate their benefits for enhanced disaster risk governance supported by innovative technical frameworks to access, transform and integrate data and models into customised workflows for creating actionable solutions. The Real World Labs ensure the project continuously and actively involves key stakeholders in the co-development process and address topical problems of multi-hazard risk management and Climate Change Adaptation to maximise impacts.

DIRECTED builds on a highly interactive transdisciplinary knowledge co-production process and an innovative digital architecture for process integration and analytics aimed at facilitating enhanced knowledge-based dialogues, communication, cooperation and “interoperability” on the three levels that are essential for integrating Disaster Risk

Management (DRM) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) related to extreme climate events in a multi-scale and multi-risk perspective: 1) Governance interoperability, 2) Information interoperability, and 3) Data and model interoperability (Figure 1).

Figure 1: DIRECTED project concept.

For this aim, experts and expertise from the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) provided from within the consortium will play a crucial role. Governance interoperability seeks to integrate relevant actors, responders and stakeholders across institutions, sectors and scales through suitable governance and enabling mechanisms, suggestions for adjusted legal frameworks and tailored responsibilities and financing arrangements. Information interoperability pursues a verifiably and timely information exchange between all phases of the DRM cycle through improved dialogues and communication between DRM and CCA communities across multiple levels, such as resolving issues in understanding early warnings and turning relevant information into effective and coordinated actions.

In this regard, model-based information such as flood forecasts, disaster risk assessments, climate projections and cost-benefit analyses play a critical role in decision-support in different phases of the integrated DRM-CCA cycle. Data and model interoperability addresses the need for combining data and models (e.g. multi-risk), including proprietary resources, from/at different domains, providers, resolutions, vintages, sources, formats (and more) into highly customized DRM and CCA workflows given the frequent absence of standards, and the lack of a common understanding and infrastructure. This includes but is

not limited to differences with respect to purpose, spatio-temporal scales, resolutions and conflicting model assumptions.

DIRECTED aims to pave the way for the generic use of existing state-of-the-art data and models combined by means of open standards for information and data exchange; and to demonstrate the feasibility thereof when available tools are made interoperable. Four RWLs form the core of our DIRECTED approach and frame the settings for co-creating solutions and demonstrating integrated DRM and CCA, including our new and enhanced tools and processes.

Our four laboratories cover representative European geographies (Scandinavia, Central and Eastern Europe and the Mediterranean) and are characterized by a diversity of challenges from extreme climate events (including compound events), multi-risks, climate adaptation options, scales (from local to regional), and institutional and legal settings. This approach ensures that co-designing solutions to real-world challenges is central, and that stakeholder involvement occurs throughout the project.

1.2 Project partners

The DIRECTED Project has brought together a team of collaborators that cover different areas of work including physical and social science research organisations and sit in a range of different sectors including (R) Research, (L) local or regional authorities, (P) practitioners, (C) commercial / private sector (See Table 1). As a group, from a dissemination and communication perspective, we have large existing networks in the research & academic, commercial, Local authorities and emergency services who we intend to engage, disseminate and where appropriate involve in the Project. We also intend to grow these networks through different communication platforms and techniques. This will be laid out later in this report.

Table 1: List of participating partners in the DIRECTED project consortium; (R) Research, (L) local or regional authorities, (P) practitioners, (C) commercial / private sector.

N°	Role	Sector	Short name	Legal name	Country
1	CO O	R	TUBS	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET BRAUNSCHWEIG	DE
2	BEN	R	PIK	POTSDAM-INSTITUT FUR KLIMAFOLGENFORSCHUNG EV	DE
3	BEN	R	DTU	DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	DK
4	BEN	C	GECO	GECOSISTEMA SRL	IT
5	BEN	R	RIFS	RESEARCH INSTITUTE FOR SUSTAINABILITY	DE
6	BEN	R	UCC	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK	IE
7	BEN	L	REGIONH	REGION HOVEDSTADEN	DK
8	BEN	P	ARSTPC-ER	AGENZIA REGIONALE PER LA SICUREZZATERRITORIALE E LA PROTEZIONE CIVILE	IT
9	BEN	C	G&C	GENILLARD & CO GMBH	DE
10	BEN	R	IIASA	INTERNATIONALES INSTITUT FUER ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMANALYSE	AT
11	BEN	L	EV	ERFTVERBAND	DE
12	BEN	P	ZSRT	ZALA KULONLEGES MENTOK ES ONKENTES TUZOLTO EGYSULET	HU
13	BEN	P	ARPAE	AGENZIA REGIONALE PER LA PREVENZIONE, L'AMBIENTE E L'ENERGIA DELL'EMILIA-ROMAGNA	IT
14	BEN	R	GFZ	HELMHOLTZ ZENTRUM POTSDAM DEUTSCHESGEOFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM GFZ	DE
15	BEN	C	52N	52 NORTH SPATIAL INFORMATION RESEARCH GMBH	DE
16	AP	R	ETH	EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH	CH
17	AP	C	OASIS	OASIS HUB LIMITED	UK
18	AP	R	SEI	SEI OXFORD OFFICE LIMITED	UK

1.3 Expected Outcomes & Impacts

The Directed Project has set itself some ambitious objectives to achieve within the four years of the Project and beyond.

1.3.1 Outcomes and indicators of scale and significance

Outcome 1 Improved dialogue and cooperation among scientific and technical communities, stakeholders, policymakers and local communities in the field of extreme climate events and associated events (e.g. forest fires, droughts, floods, heatwaves and storms) and Disaster Risk Reduction.

Output 1: Using the Risk-Tandem Assessment Technique (

Figure 6) we will increase the interactions, co-exploration, coproduction with transdisciplinary stakeholders in the DRM/ CCA sectors (including first & second responders, planners, scientists, media, utilities, social services & NGO's) - through the creation of four Real World Labs – assisting the development of long-term working relationships; understanding roles, responsibilities, dependencies, barriers to improvements and efficiencies needed.

Indicator 1: Real World Lab case studies and summary reports used by DRM/CCA stakeholders for planning purposes.

Scale of contribution – The Risk-Tandem Assessment Technique will enable the building of consensus approaches towards Disaster Risk Management, reduction and climate adaptation for the four regions of the Real World Labs: the Danube River Basin, covering the multiple municipalities – in city and countryside contexts, Copenhagen and Capital Region, Emilia-Romagna Region, Italy, and the Rhine-Erft Region, Germany.

Outcome 2 Enhanced community engagement for prevention, preparedness, response, recovery and learning to extreme climate events by strengthening knowledge and involvement of volunteers linked to recognised organisations into the planning, design and implementation of prevention, including building with nature, preparedness and emergency response activities.

Output 2: A Co-production methodology for disaster resilience will be developed and used by at least two municipalities increasing the connections and engagement of volunteers in the planning, design and implementation of prevention, including building with nature, preparedness and emergency response activities.

Indicator 2: Co-produced planning reports

Scale of contribution – Disaster Resilience Planning Reports will be developed and included in local planning in Copenhagen and Capital Region, Emilia-Romagna Region, Italy and the Rhine-Erft Region, Germany.

Outcome 3 Strengthening of Disaster Risk Reduction and resilience building through innovative use of media means, namely by examining the potential of new communication tools and apps for better preparedness and response.

Output 3a: A Data Fabric/ mesh/ ecosystem – and linked tools, developed into workflows, that enable the rapid delivery of relevant information, data, maps etc. to relevant stakeholders e.g. maps of potential areas at risk using forecast information for risk assessment to early responders or communications for mass media delivered with warning visualisations or integration of data sources for Climate Change Adaptation etc.

Indicator 3a: Workflows will be utilised by Real World Lab participant stakeholders to improve current processes.

Output 3b: Visualisations – Simple communications in the form of visualisations of threat level, action required and how to get communications on hazard events will be developed for the general public consumption – enabling faster actions of citizens to prepare for climate events – for 3 municipalities. Indicator 3b: Visualisations disseminated to general public online, social media &/or via printed mailings.

Scale of contribution – The Data Fabric/ mesh/ ecosystem will provide a prototype system and tools enabling replicable workflows of work including multiple stakeholder organisations, all types of quantitative and qualitative: including data, maps, visualisations and text formats for communications to diverse stakeholders. The system is intended to radically reform and improve the management and communications for disaster management, risk assessment and adaptation planning enabling actionable decisions using complex and multiple data sources. We intend for these tools to be replicated across Europe and beyond.

Outcome 4 Overview of existing knowledge, tools and development of new tools (innovative data collection, satellite data, data harmonisation, artificial-intelligence tools, algorithms, sensors and decision-aid approaches) for early warning, response and resilience / adaptation to be demonstrated in the framework of real-case scenarios designed for training addressed to first and second responders, (national, regional, local) authorities and populations. The overview should document how legal and ethical rules of operation as well as fundamental rights such as privacy and protection of personal data are taken into account.

Output 4: Forecasting and risk assessment, and adaptation tools made interoperable to increase functionality and multi-risk outputs necessary for seamless early warning, risk assessment and risk reduction strategy decision-making. The tool collaboration will have the capability to be used for training and implementation of Disaster Risk Management.

Indicator 4: Use of interoperable systems by DRM and CCA authorities to assist training, planning and decision making.

Scale of contribution – From within the Project a range of existing tools in flood risk assessment, adaptation planning, forecasting, citizen App will be enabled to become interoperable – thus improving multi-hazard risk assessment capabilities and functions – on top of this the work on interoperability is set to develop a standard so that multiple tools and data from beyond the project can also become interoperable in the future and in doing so improve access to and functionality of single use tools into a multi-hazard ecosystem for decision support for multiple stakeholders across sectors and European regions and beyond.

Outcome 5 Based on the demonstrations, development of new governance strategies and robust decision-support methodologies for integrated risk reduction and improved adaptation to climate extreme events.

Output 5: Data Fabric/ mesh that enables the sharing, management and communication to relevant stakeholders in useable formats of complex information, data, maps and risk assessment – managed through one multi-partner system. Indicator 5: – Governance workflows agreed by stakeholders and implemented into management system/ Data Fabric.

Scale of contribution – Governance workflows on a range of case studies will be implemented in the Danube River Basin, covering the multiple municipalities – in city and countryside contexts, Emilia-Romagna Region, Italy, Copenhagen and Capital Region, and the Rhine-Erft Region, Germany.

Outcome 6 Improved understanding of enablers and barriers to multi-risk governance frameworks and multi-risk thinking, by involving interdisciplinary teams in different fields, particularly the social and behavioural sciences.

Output 6: Policy brief on risk governance in the context of DRR and CCA highlighting barriers and potential solutions to improve multi-risk governance.

Indicator 6: Uptake of recommendations from policy brief by at least one DRR/CCA agency

Scale of contribution – The EC and national policy-makers in Germany, Hungary and Italy will have access to findings and results of the DIRECTED Project. We envisage this will assist future governance of disasters and climate adaptation planning.

Outcome 7 Cost-benefit or cost-effectiveness analyses of investment and regulatory strategies to protect people and nature in vulnerable areas.

Output 7: Cost-benefit analysis of climate adaptation/ disaster reduction measures made for at least 2 municipalities during the project.

Indicator 7: Cost-benefit analysis of climate adaptation/ disaster reduction measures for at least 2 municipality used in future planning document or applications for adaptation funding for climate adaptation/ Disaster Risk Reduction.

Scale of contribution – Two municipalities will have conducted cost/ benefit analysis of potential climate adaptation actions enabling a strong needs analysis of multiple climate adaptation solutions that increases the potential for investment.

Beyond to Project outcomes above the project is intended to lead to a range of intended impacts some of which will begin during the Project and others that should continue beyond the life of the Project.

Figure 2: DIRECTED Data Fabric schematic representation of the data infrastructure.

1.3.2 Intended Impacts

Scientific: The DIRECTED Project will assist the scientific community in stocktaking of standards for the interoperability of data and models, identifying gaps and requirements to exchange information between different phases of DRM/ CCA cycle and across hazards and integrating quantitative and qualitative indicators. This will assist the scientific community with providing an interoperability framework that enables future tool development that can become part of a wider network for decision making data, tools and systems increasing the potential to provide actionable intelligence based on data and information from multiple sources by the DRR and CCA community.

Through the production of workflow processes within the Project – the provision at what stages, to whom and in what format scientific information is included and communicated will be an impact of the Project providing collaboration between sectors that do not traditionally have access to science and scientists directly, likely to become a policy recommendation moving forward, thus increasing access to actionable science by all levels of government and society.

Economic: the DIRECTED Project outputs will contribute a range of economic impacts in the future:

- The breakdown of silos e.g. between cross boundary municipalities, between multiple stakeholder groups in the DRR/CCA process will increase the economic efficiency of work and linked funding by creating more seamless workflows, preventing duplication of spend on the same actions with the potential to more carefully budget and target spend across actors and locations.
- Work that has enabled the interoperability of multiple forms of data and tools into producing multi-risk, risk assessment and Climate Change Adaptation solutions plus linked cost benefit analysis will increase the potential to implement adaptation actions, targeted at locations most at risk, thus reducing the overall spend required to enable increased resilience by society.
- Losses from climate disasters are reduced through enhanced Disaster Risk Reduction based on preventive actions, better societal preparedness and resilience and improved Disaster Risk Management in a systemic way – with the potential to reduce losses significantly over time in the regions of billions of Euros.

Societal: The DIRECTED Project outputs will also contribute to societal impacts in the future:

- Losses from climate disasters are reduced through enhanced Disaster Risk Reduction based on preventive actions, better societal preparedness and resilience and improved Disaster Risk Management in a systemic way.
- Enabling scientific outputs to more rapidly be utilised by DRR/CCA actors and also directly communicated to the general public – helping to inform potential for damage and then actions required across society including at household & business levels to reduce the impact of climate-related catastrophes.

- Supporting first, second and third responders with forecast and risk assessment information they need to utilise emergency services more effectively – understanding the likelihood of the most impacted zones after a disaster and conditions associated with that emergency e.g. flood levels, types of properties and multiple other data sources as brought together by interoperable tools and the Data Fabric/ mesh.
- Supporting first, second and third responders with training materials enabling more efficient responses to climate emergencies.

1.4 Target Groups for Communication and Dissemination

DRR and CCA communities involve multiple stakeholder groups, all requiring information for different purposes and at different levels of communication. Likewise, the work undertaken involves different time dimensional needs e.g. disaster information during a disaster and the need for risk reduction and climate adaptation planning. We seek to reduce complexity and increase efficiency to access the relevant information and data needs through understanding and creating appropriate workflows where we will seek to link appropriate climate science outputs and information to make operational decisions at the appropriate time, e.g. risk reduction and adaptation planning or for training and preparation or operational response. We have carefully selected representational organisations of our target groups to be directly involved as co-production, co-design partners in the Project.

Our target groups include:

- 1) First and second responders
- 2) Regional and municipal civil authorities - including disaster management, planning authorities and cross regional municipalities
- 3) Physical and social scientific organisations - those who work in climate change, natural disaster sciences and damage and loss, governance and innovation
- 4) The general public - will be mainly be represented by municipalities

The Real World Labs will invite other local stakeholders including utility companies, NGO's, health and social care organisations to become part of the consultations. We perceive that the four RWL's: in the Danube catchment basin, Germany, Italy and Scandinavia will be representative of stakeholders from across Europe to ensure the potential for scalability of governance structures, the use of interoperable tools and management via Data Fabric/ mech digital architectures.

Beyond the work of the Project directly, we intend to engage stakeholders who will benefit from knowledge of the techniques used in the Project, as well as the tools used within the system and the Data Fabric itself from the four communities named above, and extended beyond the regions involved in the Project

2 Dissemination and communications tools and processes in the DIRECTED Project

Oasis Hub will lead on the formal communications of the Project in conjunction with all partners in the DIRECTED Project. Formal and social media communications will be centralised through Oasis Hub with dissemination of news, articles, blogs, social media messaging through Oasis Hub networks and the partner organisations in the Project. Oasis Hub has experienced science communication and innovation professionals thus DIRECTED will communicate professional level materials aimed at non-specialist audiences through a diary of planned releases related to the different stages of the project. Some releases will be translated into a range of European languages linked to relevant target audiences.

In addition, as far as possible we will try to use every day, inclusive language to convey messaging, avoiding as much jargon as possible, to attempt to provide access to all through the language we use. This will also help with read softwares that assist visually impaired readers to access our work.

We have designed a communications and dissemination process that is more broadly divided into the different stages the Project will go through as follows in Table 2 below.

Table 2: DIRECTED communications timeline.

Phase 1 Oct 2022 to March 2023	Phase 2 March 2023 to March 2024	Phase 3 March 2024 to March 2025	Phase 4 March 2025 to March 2026	Phase 5 March 2026 to October 2026
<p>Communications strategy developed</p> <p>Project launch communications</p> <p>Start of Project Blog – quarterly blog posts to continue to end of the Project</p> <p>Bi-weekly social media posts began and continued to the end of the Project e.g. stories, plans etc.</p> <p>Website development</p> <p>Brand development</p>	<p>Communications on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project events • Workshops • Processes and techniques and the physical and social scientists/ themselves • Building a picture of the people involved in Directed stakeholder involvement and outcomes during this phase <p>Continued social media dissemination</p> <p>Beginning of conference dissemination</p>	<p>Communications on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early scientific & governance and process • Findings from market research and stakeholder needs assessment • Real World Lab reports <p>Continued conference dissemination</p> <p>Continued social media dissemination</p> <p>Case study creation</p>	<p>Research publications and related news and articles</p> <p>Training material and programme on use of tools and systems</p> <p>Webinar series with physical and social scientists</p> <p>Continued social media dissemination</p> <p>Media pack creation & dissemination (press releases for international media)</p>	<p>Policy-maker meetings, policy briefs.</p> <p>Conference dissemination of results</p> <p>Continued social media dissemination</p>

2.1 Responsibilities for communication and dissemination

When communicating with our target audience, the main spokespeople of DIRECTED Project are the following:

- The **Project Manager** and the **WP 6 Lead** will be responsible for communicating about the project and its results and progress on behalf of the project consortium;
- The **WP 6 Lead** and team members responsible for the overall communication strategy on behalf of the project consortium. WP 6 Lead and team members are also in charge of encouraging Partners to take part in communication activities within the project;
- The **WP Leads** are responsible for the communication of the results of the project within the frame of their specific WP;
- The **Real World Lab Leads** (WP 1) are responsible for communication about the Real World Labs within the respective geographic scope;
- **All Partners** are responsible for communication about their involvement in the project.

Breaches of these responsibilities shall be reported to either the Project Coordinator or WP 6 Lead and mitigation of any issues will be actioned. If an organisation does not take part in communications and dissemination activities as beneficiaries are obliged to do under the grant agreement, without prior permission not to be involved in communications and dissemination, the EU Project Officer will be informed.

2.2 Communications

2.2.1 Project Launch

A Project Launch has been conducted in conjunction with our first meeting in November, 2022. A social media campaign was conducted by all of the partner making the announcement on multiple social media channels and websites.

2.2.2 Project Branding & Website

Project branding has been developed to enable easy recognition of the DIRECTED Project and to ensure that the Project is recognised as one rather than a series of smaller projects. The DIRECTED Logo and branding will be used on all DIRECTED communications.

Figure 3: DIRECTED logo design.

We have designed branded communication templates for reports, policy briefs, conference posters and pull-outs using DIRECTED branding which all of the participants in the project will use.

Importantly we have designed a DIRECTED Project website. The website includes a wide range of communication channels including a regular blog, news, publications, reports, videos, podcasts and webinars. To ease and assist communications, partners will be able to copy links or download materials and post to organisational media outlets.

Figure 4: DIRECTED project website. Learn more under <https://directedproject.eu/>.

The Project URL can be found here: <https://directedproject.eu/>

The site will disseminate full information and progress of the Project, as well as more contextual information on climate Disaster Risk Management and climate adaptation.

Figure 5: Central communications and dissemination hub on the DIRECTED website. Media access under <https://directedproject.eu/media/>.

In addition, we are making it a central communications and dissemination hub in that all of our social media will be connected to the website, project reports, videos and podcasts, webinars, publications and presentations can be stored and viewed on the site (Figure 5).

Table 3: Target for communication action.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
All	30,000 Users over 4 years	Users from google analytics	Outcomes 1,2,3,4,5,6,7 Broad communication of reports, videos, podcasts, webinars, papers, news, presentations

2.2.3 Real World Labs/ Case Study Creation

Case studies will be developed as a part of the Real World Labs. The idea of the case studies is to publish information and experiences of grassroots professionals when working on climate Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation and include process successes and failures and communications issues that have occurred during and after disasters and in the facilitation of cross border climate adaptation planning and action. We hope this will enable other professionals in DRR/CCA to recognise the friction in their processes and potential ways to overcome and improve these.

The case study will be particularly focused on those Real World Labs that have recently experienced extreme events - Emilia-Romagna, the May 2023 extreme flood events and Rhine-Erft, July 2021 extreme floods and will involve the on-the-ground stakeholders in developing local level accounts of what occurred, how it was managed and how improvements in future could occur. This deliverable is particularly linked to D1.3. Case Study Development.

Table 4: Target for case study creation.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
1) First and second responders 2) Regional and municipal civil authorities - including disaster management, planning authorities and cross regional municipalities 3) Physical and social scientific organisations	Case studies downloaded or viewed through social media or through specialist publications by 100x CCA & DRM professionals	Downloads and views from website	Outcomes 1,2,3,4,6

Work Packages engaged:

- WP 1 Emilia-Romagna and Rhine-Erft participants
- WP 2 Models – SaferPlaces and Rim2D
- WP 3
- WP 4
- WP 5 Linked to developing training packages
- WP 6 Lead

2.2.4 Visualisations

Visualisations for the general public and volunteers will be designed for effective communications of stages of risk decision for public information to enable a simple understanding on the processes of risk e.g. prepare, evacuate, where to find official communication, level of flood that sparks decision stages – these will be designed in local languages and for the local context for the RWL's. Visualisations will be developed for volunteers to aid their understanding of go and no-go areas during an event.

The visualisations will be generated through using the Data Fabric in WP 5 and the data and tools found in WP 2.

Other visualisations that may be generated will be based around understanding the Risk-Tandem Framework processes to enable training and capacity development with WP 1 and developed through WP 3 and WP 4.

Table 5: Target for visualisation for the general public.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
General Public/ volunteer	Reach 2000 households in the RWL case study area	Downloads / or public dissemination numbers	Outcome 3b General public/ volunteers informed of disaster decision-making process and where to get information.
Disaster Management professionals	To be provided to participants in capacity development training	Numbers at capacity development training events	Outcome 3b Visualisation that explain the process of the Risk Tandem Framework provided to participants in capacity development and training.

Work Packages engaged:

- WP 1
- WP 2
- WP 3
- WP 4
- WP 5

2.2.5 Social Media

New DIRECTED Project social media have been created and developed including;

- LinkedIn discussion group – we will use this as a key dissemination forum inviting DRR & CCA specialists to the forum to engage and collaborate with us. We will also use LinkedIn to poll members on key questions that will benefit our work – thus gaining input from a wider range of stakeholders. We see linked in as the medium to engage a large network of professionals in the fields of DRR and CCA
Find us on LinkedIn - <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/14155514/>
- YouTube for video
Find us on YouTube - @directedproject
- Twitter & Mastodon – we will build communities in both Twitter and Mastodon. We are using both as it is unclear whether Twitter will keep its top status and whether it will be able to continue long-term. Mastodon also targets specialist user groups. These channels will primarily be aimed at communicating to the general public
Find us on Twitter and Mastodon
Twitter - @DirectedProj
Mastodon - <https://vmst.io/> @DirectedProject
- Instagram – has been chosen as it is used by the younger people. We will be posting small videocasts and visualisations informing people about our project. Again, we will use this to inform new audiences in particular younger people.
Find us on Instagram - <https://www.instagram.com/directedproject/>

These channels will be developed by following other stakeholder organisations and relevant influencers as well as linking to our partners social medias. Relevant hashtags will be identified and used to attract other relevant followers.

We will also communicate information throughout our project members existing social media channels some beneficiaries having large existing members/ followers and link to these channels with social media posts and encourage each institution to share posts and create their own posts regarding the Project. Table 6. shows existing members social media reach.

Table 6: Existing channels to communicate DIRECTED information and news.

Name of Beneficiary	Channel	Link or address	Website/ Newsletter Reach	Followers/ members
Oasis Hub	Twitter	@Oasis_HUB		3000
	Newsletter		4100	
	Website	https://oasishub.co/	20000	
TUB	Twitter	@HydRiv_LWI		33
	Mastodon	@hydriw@mas.to		10
	Website	https://www.tu-braunschweig.de/en/lwi/hydriw		
PIK	Eventual press releases	https://www.pik-potsdam.de/en/news/latest-news		
DTU	Website	https://dtu.dk		
	Twitter	https://twitter.com/DTUtweet		17103
	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/school/technical-university-of-denmark		161698
	Facebook	www.facebook.dk/dtuduk		40605
	Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/dtuduk/		16086
GECO	Website	https://gecosistema.com/		
	Twitter	@gecosistema		335
	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/gecosistema/		585
	Website SaferPlaces	https://saferplaces.co/		
	Twitter SaferPlaces	@SaferPlacesCKIC		288
RIFS	Website	https://www.rifs-potsdam.de/en		
	Twitter	@rifs_Potsdam		8800
	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/rifs-potsdam/mycompany/		9616
SEI	Twitter	@weADAPT1		7403
	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/in/weadapt/		3202
	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/c/WeadaptOrg		
	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/weadaptgroup/		
	Website	www.weADAPT.org		150,000
	SEI Twitter	@SEIclimate		48,000
UCC	Twitter	https://twitter.com/MaREIcentre		8800
	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/marei/mycompany/		4400
	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCCVXK0okrR0aawxUGkGZvvg		
	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/MaREIcentre		
	Website	https://www.marei.ie/research/projects/		
	UCC Twitter	https://twitter.com/UCC		59800
REGIONH	Twitter	https://twitter.com/RegionH_RegUdv		1.611
	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/center-for-regional-udvikling/		881
	Website	www.regionh.dk		
ARSTPC-ER	Web Site	Homepage -- Agenzia per la sicurezza territoriale -- e la protezione civile (regione.emilia-romagna.it)		
	YouTube	ARSTPC - YouTube		
	Facebook	Facebook		
	Newsletter	https://regioneer.it/ya563f3b		
	website		LifePrimes – More Resilience Less Risk	
G&C	G&Co Website	News Genillard & Co (genillard-co.com)	1200	
	G&Co LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/genillard-&-co-gmbh/ +G&Co Staff		900
IIASA	IIASA website	https://iiasa.ac.at/projects/directed	2000	
EV	EV Website (not yet create)	www.erftverband.de/forschung-und-entwicklung/		
	EV LinkedIn	linkedin.com/company/erftverband		422
	EV facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Erftverband	reach 96.629, site views 10.591	1.394
52° North	Website	https://52north.org/news/		
	Twitter	@FiveTwoN		850
	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/52-north-gmbh/		382
	Fosstodon	@52North@fosstodon.org		
ZSRT ARPAE	Web Site ARPAE	https://www.arpae.it/it		
	Web Site AllertameteoER	https://allertameteo.regione.emilia-romagna.it/web/guest/homepage/		
	Twitter	@AllertaMeteoRER		
	Telegram	https://t.me/AllertameteoEMR		

Oasis Hub will use its social media communities on Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube (where video is available) to communicate messaging. Existing audiences on Oasis Hub Twitter (mixed community of specialists in: insurance/ reinsurance, scientists, economists, climate change specialists (including policy), risk management & reduction, Disaster Risk Reduction, remote sensing, flood risk, climate adaptation, sustainable development, natural hazards, climate risk, Climate Change Adaptation, big data in both public and private sectors) and LinkedIn (mainly insurance, reinsurance and finance specialists), partner, other beneficiary communications.

New audiences will be targeted through linking to particular influencers in relevant sectors – new target sectors will include risk managers in municipalities, local authorities and services, policy-makers, DRR professionals and local planning departments and specific targets as

they become clear after the ideation/ market research/ user needs engagement in the Project.

Table 7: Target for social media.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impacts
All	Reach users: LinkedIn – 200 external DRR & CCA professionals YouTube – create at least five short videos and gain 100 subscribers on YouTube Twitter and Mastodon develop followers on both platforms of 500 Instagram gain 500 followers	Analytic indicators provided on each platform	Outcomes 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Work Packages engaged:

- WP 6 Lead
- All WPs as content providers and distributors

2.2.6 Video, Podcasts & Webinars

Webinar series will be designed for specific sectors in phase 4 of the project communications with the physical and social scientists, and local governance actors engaged in the project, presenting and talking to specifically targeted sectors and then further engagement by Oasis Hub of attendees in encouraging the use of outputs by those stakeholders engaged in the webinars. Oasis Hub webinars attract in the region of 200 people per webinar. In addition, the recordings of the webinars will be shared on YouTube and the DIRECTED website.

Short videos and podcasts will record a range of aspects of the Project including a short introductory video and then longer more detailed videos as the Project progresses.

Table 8: Target for audio visual media.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impacts
Webinars 1) First and second responders 2) Regional and municipal civil authorities - including disaster management, planning authorities and cross regional municipalities 3) Physical and social scientific organisations	100 attendees x 4 webinars aimed at specialist groups	Attendees engagement as collected in Zoom analytics Resulting engagements/ links/ collaboration after webinars	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7
Videos & podcasts All	At least 6 x videos and podcasts placed on website and YouTube & Instagram – and shared on other	Analytics from google analytics, YouTube, Instagram, Twitter, Mastodon on message containing videos or podcast	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

	platforms		
	Reaching 600+ viewers		

Work Packages engaged:

- WP 6 Lead
- All WPs as content providers and distributors

2.2.7 Quarterly Blog

Blogs will be used as a medium to fully engage audiences in a more detailed fashion. These will include information about the Projects, about results and discussions of Real World Labs, what a Data Fabric is, information on the scientific tools within the Project and much more.

Blogs will be posted at a minimum on a quarterly basis, at the beginning of the Project but will increase as activity and outputs increase in the Project.

All Work Packages will be involved in writing or providing information for the Blog.

Table 9: Target for blog articles.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
Specialist users – including DRR & CCA professionals	20,000 articles views on specialist channels	Article views	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Work Packages involved:

- All work pages as the plans included writing blogs connected to each Work Package.

2.2.8 Mass Media and Media Pack Creation

Press releases will be released on activities that may be of interest to broad audiences to local medias on the activities of the Real World Labs. Later on in the Project as results become available and more outcomes are achieved editorials will be pitched to specialist medias e.g. insurance, climate change and DRR specialist publications.

We will also disseminate press releases/ radio/ podcast ideas to local radio stations to enable wider audiences to understand the work of DIRECTED within the Real World Labs as well as to engage the general public and audiences that find print and digital medias difficult to access. Of course, it will be the radio stations decision if they wish to do a slot involving DIRECTED content.

Media Packs – will be designed for digital distribution to specialist on-line media portals e.g. insurance magazines, EU Adapt and other EU comms platforms, and medias targeted at Cities and public authorities and the international media. These packs will contain case studies and press releases related to specific outputs of the DIRECTED Project. A major media campaign will occur in the 4th phase of the communications plan when results are ready to be published. If we believe there are stories that will potentially be high profile media we will inform the EU Project Officer in the planning stage or if something is picked up unexpectedly, as soon as possible.

Table 10: Target for mass media packs.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
Mass media – General Public	25 Media packs downloaded/ provided to media	Articles published	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7
Press releases provided to local media including print, digital and radio	4 press articles of radio segments developed	Articles/ radio segments	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Work Packages engaged:

- WP 6 Lead
- WP 1 Local level media outputs
- All project partners may be involved depending on specific media interests

2.3 Dissemination

2.3.1 Tool Demonstrations

As a part of the programme there will be a need to demonstrate a range of newly developed/ adapted climate change risk assessment, Climate Change Adaptation and disaster management tools within the Real-world labs and the organisations represented in them. This will enable the DRR and CCA practitioners to more clearly understand some of the new tools developed in the previous H2020 programmes and via other programmes and companies to seek advice from CCA and DRR practitioners how they would like the tools to be made interoperable and what additional parameters should be added to make them more useful.

These demonstrations are particularly linked to the tools and models named under WP 2 and Data Fabric in WP 5 - but also WP 3 & 4 with regards to the Risk-Tandem Framework.

Table 11: Target for tool demonstrations.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
Specialist audiences	At least 16 presentations of tools & services made to real world practitioners	Number of presentations and members in the audience	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Work Packages engaged:

- WP 2, WP 5 and WP 3 & 4

2.3.2 Stakeholder engagement in co-design and co-production

DIRECTED will put co-creation and co-production at its heart, by applying the Tandem approach of transdisciplinary knowledge co-production with a risk governance lens, resulting in Risk-Tandem. The Tandem philosophy represents a major shift away from a focus on 'products' to a transdisciplinary knowledge co-production 'process' in which co-design and collaborative learning is the defining characteristic, and both stakeholders and modellers alike build their capacity to understand the decision context and the potential of data and tools. The use of Tandem guides stakeholders from across the science-society interface, with diverse knowledge, expertise and experience to collaborate, co-design activities and co-produce knowledge and data for models and tools to provide context-specific input to Climate Change Adaptation plans and policies. With a risk governance lens, Risk-Tandem will act as a lever to bring knowledge on co-design and co-development to the core of model development processes to support more effective decision-making and serve as a mechanism for facilitating participation, engagement and communication. Transdisciplinary co-production, knowledge exchange and learning processes will be designed to enhance and reconcile key aspects of "interoperability" that currently serves as a barrier for effective DRR.

Figure 6 shows how the current Tandem Framework supports different Work Packages in Directed. The Risk-Tandem Framework will be a version tailored for application in the RWLs and further refined and improved over the lifetime of the project.

This dissemination action is particularly linked to WP 1 Real World Labs and WP 3 Risk Governance and WP 4 Risk-Tandem Framework.

Figure 6: Directed Work Packages linked to the Tandem Framework.

Work Packages engaged:

- WP 3 and WP 1

Table 12: Target for stakeholder engagement.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
Specialist audiences	Detailed stakeholder engagement for co-design and co-production in conjunction with four Real World Labs	Number of specialists involved in workshops	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

2.3.3 Policy Briefs & Policy-maker Meetings

Policy briefs will be created using the results of the DIRECTED Project to make recommendations towards EU and local disaster risk, economic and climate adaptation policies. A briefing of the results of the Project will be conducted in phase 5 of the Project to relevant EU Departments and Executive Agencies (DG’s) – we will also seek an understanding whether relevant DG’s would seek to be kept up-to-date in the progress of the project e.g. how & when. Likewise, policy briefs can also be distributed amongst local level

policy stakeholders to guide policy as appropriate. We will also distribute policy information through the CMINE networks and joint activities with other Horizon Europe Projects.

WP6 will lead the co-ordination of these actions - but all Work Packages will feed into policy recommendations.

Table 13: Target for policy briefs.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
Policy-makers and senior civil servants	At end of project deliver policy implications for governance and transfer of climate change science to the DRR/CCA communities across Europe	Number of policy-makers and senior civil servants attending meetings Downloads of policy briefs	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Work Packages engaged;

- WP 6 Lead
- WP 1, WP 2, WP 3, WP 4, WP 5 – content/ findings

2.3.4 DIRECTED e-Learning Portal

Development of training programmes that combine information and learning related elements of governance frameworks that can be supported by innovative technical frameworks to access, transform and integrate data and models into customised workflows for creating actionable solutions.

Programmes will target vocational long-life training to support the Real World Labs, practitioners support materials and provide support and help build risk and adaptation solutions, especially those identified by Real World Labs.

In order to perpetuate learning programmes, a co-designed and co-developed “Training of Trainers” programme will be developed through a dedicated workshop with trainers, and curriculum developed in response to needs, so that capability beyond the DIRECTED project is ensured. Workshops delivered both in-person and online will be highly participatory and practical, focusing on techniques, tools and tips of training management, with participants themselves designing, delivering and critiquing methods.

Building on the Gaps and Opportunity Assessment (D6.3) and related Knowledge Transfer Plans put forward in the report. A suitable e-Learning portal will be identified during the project to deposit and make available all training materials produced; this will increase the ability to deliver 21st century learning and training opportunities.

Table 14: Target for e-Learning.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
<p>DRM/ CCA practitioners</p> <p>Specialist Groups</p>	<p>Co-development training of ‘Trainer of Trainers’ Programme to increase uptake of KERs (Risk-Tandem Framework and Data Fabric)and curriculum development</p>	<p>Number of Workshops</p> <p>Number of Trainees/ Attendees</p> <p>Accessibility/ Use of e-Learning materials</p>	<p>Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7</p>
<p>Technical specialists (Data Stewards)</p>	<p>Availability of technical guidance to guide users on implementing the Data Fabric and suite of models/tools.</p>	<p>Number of specialised technical trainings in RWLs</p> <p>Open accessibility guidebooks (Readme, Jupyter Notebooks)</p>	<p>Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7</p>
<p>(Early Career) researchers/ scientists</p>	<p>Early career researchers and scientists engaged a assessing learning/ training materials</p>	<p>Number of early career researchers engaged through 1) summer schools 2) guest lectures 3) other</p>	<p>Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7</p>

Work Packages engaged;

- WP 6 Lead
- WP 1, WP 2, WP 3, WP 4, WP 5 - Content providers

2.3.5 Published Papers

Academic journals – academic partners will target online high impact journals with academic research and new methodologies produced by the Project.

Table 15: Target for academic publishing.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
Scientists & Researchers	Publication of at least 2 papers in high impact journals	Papers published Citations	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Work Packages engaged:

- WP 2, WP 3, WP 4 – for specific topic areas
- All – for project wide papers

2.3.6 Conference Attendance

Partners will attend and develop sessions for academic, public sector and business conferences to promote the new methodologies, data, tools/ tool-kits/ training packs and reports etc.

These conferences will include EGU, COP, ICLEI, Disaster Risk, ECCA, DRR and CCA conferences – to target specific audiences where relevant. Where possible stands will be located at larger conferences promoting the full outputs of the Project in the later part of the Project.

A short conference strategy will be designed to ensure that information is disseminated as widely as possible to target audiences.

Conferences accepted for in 2023 include:

Table 16: Conference antecedence in 2023.

Conference to be attended	Name of Session	Date & venue	Audience
The Day of Hydrology –Tag der Hydrologie	Session 5 Future water governance	March 21–23, 2023 Ruhr-University Bochum in Germany	Specialist Audience - Water
European Geosciences Union (EGU)2023	Innovations and ground-breaking technologies for natural hazard risk modelling,	23–28 April 2023 Vienna, Austria	Scientists & researchers

	management and financing Session currently being merged		
Geospatial World Forum	"Collaborative models for fit-for-purpose knowledge co-creation".	5 May, 2023 Rotterdam	Specialist Audience – Geospatial Professionals
6th European Climate Change Adaptation Conference	Tbc	June 19 - 21st 2023, Dublin	Specialist Audience – CCA Professionals
IUGG Berlin 2023	Poster Sessions	11-20 July, 2023	Specialist Audience – Scientists & researchers
RemTech Expo - international event dedicated to protection and sustainable development on the territory, remediation of contaminated sites, coasts and ports, hydrogeological risk, climate changes, seismic risk, urban regeneration and sustainable chemical industry	Tbc	20 - 22 September 2023 Ferrara, Italy	Specialist Audience – National & Local Authorities
ECOMONDO – Green Technology Exhibition	Tbc	7 - 10 November 2023, Rimini, Italy	Specialist Audience – National & Local Authorities

Table 17: Target for conference antecedence.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
Scientists & Researchers Specialist Audiences – DRR & CCA professionals National & Local authorities	Attendance of at least 20 high impact conferences over 4 years	Attendees at sessions	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Work Packages engaged:

- WP 1
- WP 2
- WP 3
- WP 4
- WP 5

dissemination of high impact research and practical work

2.3.6 Use of EU Communications & Dissemination Platforms

We will also seek support from EC communication hubs such as Climate Adapt, weADAPT and through other departments and platforms of the EC to disseminate our communications more broadly. We will receive guidance on this from 'Next edition of the Secure Societies 'Projects to Policy Seminar' jointly organised by DG Home and REA in Brussels in June 2023.

Table 18: Target for EC communication.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
All	Publication of at least 4 articles or posts on EC platforms	Publications posted	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Work Packages engaged:

- WP 6 and WP 7 Lead
- All WP's as required

2.3.7 Data Stewardship Principles

During the DIRECTED Project a range of data will be developed and used and will be made open publicly on a range of data platforms including the DIRECTED Website itself and the open databases of beneficiary organisations. We will also produce a data directory stating where all of the data developed during the project is made publicly available. This will include both the data itself, the outputs from modelling work and maps produced.

Work Packages engaged:

- WP 2 and WP 5

Data collected through WP 3 and WP 4 will be disaggregated and anonymised where any personal details or experiences has been conveyed.

Target Groups Reached	Goal	Indicator	Aids Outcome/ Impact
All	A data directory published on the DIRECTED website and across our social media platforms	Data Directory published	Outcomes: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

3. Monitoring & Evaluation of Communication & Dissemination Impacts

3.1 Monitoring

It is well known that the monitoring of communications and dissemination is inherently difficult apart from quantitative parameters such as those associated with different social media platforms – followers, impressions, engagement etc. and website analytics etc. and yet we are all aware of the power of medias to inform, engage and influence people. For the purpose of this strategy monitoring indicators can be found in each communication and dissemination action above in the tables provided. The parameters will be collected in terms of each actions as follows in Table 19:

Table 19: Overview of communication monitoring.

Type of communication activity	Monitoring for Impact
Project Launch	Social media analytics from partners
Project branding and website	The website will set-up google analytics to record use of the platform and use google analytics to show engagement with the platform
Real World Lab/ Case Study Creation	Case study downloads from website and quotes in publications Numbers and professions attending RWL's
Visualisations	Downloads from website, views on social media
Social Media Communications	Analytics as relevant from our platforms: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● LinkedIn Group ● Twitter ● Mastodon ● Instagram ● YouTube Including followers, engagement, likes, shares, comments etc. This includes all partner analytics, where available
Video, podcasts and webinars	Views, likes & comments for videos and podcasts Webinars numbers attended, engagement (questions) & follow-ups
Quarterly Blog	Shared on all relevant social media channels and from website – relevant analytics recorded as available of channel
Media Pack Creation	Downloads from website and provided directly to Media bodies
Tool demonstrations	Numbers and user groups presented to
Stakeholder engagement in codesign and coproduction	Numbers and professions of users engaged
Policy Brief and Policy-maker meetings	Downloads & dissemination of Policy Brief Numbers and user groups attending meetings
Directed e-Learning portal	Google analytics and attendees at workshops
Published papers	Publication & citation metrics

Conference attendance	Numbers attending session and user groups
Use of EU Communication platforms	Number of Publications

As outlined in EU Guidance the result of our monitoring work will be published on the EU Horizon Europe Portal and also published in our yearly communications and dissemination reports. The monitoring system requires each partner to collect information of the communications and dissemination work they have conducted and add to the Communications and Dissemination report directly.

At the time of each yearly report, we will evaluate the monitoring work and the communication outputs to reflect on what has worked, what needs improvements to reach specified audiences and how this may reflect on impacts for the Project.

3.2 Evaluation

It is important to note that during much of the work of the DIRECTED Project there will be significant work conducted on evaluating responses from Project participants and stakeholders within WP 1,2,3,4,5. These will include evaluations on participant feedback for:

- How scientific tools can be made most interoperable for the benefit of users
- How silos and barriers can be reduced to improve governance of Disaster Management and Climate Change Adaptation
- Potential users’ views on the workflows to be implemented into the Data Fabric and Training Information

Please see above our approach to stakeholder engagement within the Risk-Tandem Framework in Section 2.2.2.

Within WP 6 a knowledge transfer plan (gaps and opportunities assessment) will be developed to assess the institutional capacity that currently exists for knowledge transfer by assessing existing training and education opportunities.

The knowledge transfer plan will be monitored and evaluated to assess the application of dissemination and exploitation activities to enable and promote the enabling ecosystem within the bounds of the RWLs to utilise the technological tools within an appropriate regulatory and economic perspective. The capacity/skills and related evolving pathways in development of governance and technological frameworks will be examined to assess how they can better address the challenges of integrated responses to risk and adaptation management.

Participants in the Real World Lab events will be asked to provide feedback on how useful they found the events. This will be done via a questionnaire at the event or via survey monkey after the event. The results will be fed back to the RWL teams who will take

appropriate actions to improve events where negative feedback is received. Later in the Project, It may also be possible to conduct a 'Tell us your Story' form of evaluation where participants in events will be asked if they took any actions after participating in the Real World Labs e.g. made new contacts, changed & improved practices, improved communication channels etc. This will be undertaken at least a month after the event. It may be possible to publish some of these sound-bites in articles or social media.

Beyond what are integral parts of the project, we will also be using our LinkedIn User Group made up of specialist professionals who will be invited to the Group or ask to attend to inform and collaborate with relevant professionals from outside of the Project but who will benefit from and have the capacity to inform the work we are doing. These viewpoints will be fed-back to the Project participants for feedback into the work that is being undertaken. LinkedIn Groups have the potential to ask questions and bring in feedback.

4. Year 1 – Dissemination & Communication Plan

The following dissemination and communication plans are guided by the reporting structure of Horizon Europe.

,Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.'

,List the communication activities carried out in the context of the project. Use the same labels used in your DEC plan.'

The tables below directly correlate to the recording structure of Horizon Europe and are the planned work of the beneficiaries.

We will undergo further yearly communications and dissemination reviews to develop and improve the communications and dissemination we are undertaking. The review and planning phases are timetabled as follows;

- September 2023
- September 2024
- September 2025
- September 2026

4.1 Year 1 – Dissemination Plan

Table 20: Dissemination plan - Year 1.

Name of Beneficiary	Dissemination Activity Name	Type of Dissemination Activity	Target Audience Reached	Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output	Status of Activity
Oasis Hub	Next edition of the Secure Societies 'Projects to Policy Seminar'	Collaboration with EU Funded Proj	EU Institutions	Dissamination of DIRECTED Project	Planned
TUBS	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	Research communities	Abstract submitted and accepted at EGU 2023 in Vienna	Ongoing
	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	Research communities	Abstract submitted and accepted at TDH 2023 in Bochum	Ongoing
	Next edition of the Secure Societies 'Projects to Policy Seminar'	Collaboration with EU Funded Proj	EU Institutions	Dissamination of DIRECTED Project	Planned
GfZ	N/A staff not yet recruited for Project - activity will be submitted in the next report				
PIK	As the first year will be needed to get the Danube model into presentable shape, no dissemination activities are planned at this early stage of the project.				
DTU	Presentation of DIRECTED to the Danish Meteorological Institute	Meetings	Research communities	in Denmark. They are currently leading a new, 6 year initiative on multi-hazard	Delivered
	Presentation of DIRECTED to the broader research community in Denmark related to v	Conferences	Research communities	Annual Meeting of the National Center for Climate Research	Planned
	Presented of DIRECTED at conference (lead by TUBS)	Conferences	Research communities	Abstract submitted and accepted at EGU 2023 in Vienna	Ongoing
	Kick-off meeting for Real World Lab (with Capital Region of Denmark)		Regional authorities	national authorities)	Planned
GECO	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	Regional authorities	REMTECH - https://www.remtechexpo.com/	Planned
	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	Local authorities	ECOMONDO https://www.ecomondo.com/	Planned
RIFS	Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty Mid-Term Conference of ESA RN22 and ISA TG04 2	Conferences	Research communities	Abstract submission to next the Midterm Conference of the research groups on	Planned
SEI	Society for Risk Analysis annual meeting 2023	Conferences	Research communities	Abstract submission to next the Society for Risk Analysis annual meeting 2023. Wa	Planned
	ToT on Tandem knowledge co-production framework	Education & training events	Local authorities	'Trainers' programme will be developed through a dedicated Workshop with	Planned
UCC	ToT modules	Other	Local authorities	learning portal and/or weADAPT.	
	EGU 2023 conference presentation	Conferences	Research communities	'boundaries and managing risk'; co-convening session "Operational forecasting	Planned
	Outreach with local schools	Education & training events	Civil society	aims/objectives).	Planned
	UNIC engaged research	Collaboration with EU Funded Proj	Local authorities	stakeholder workshops on risk communication with local authorities in Cork and	Planned
	Action Research Summer Camp (attendee)	Education & training events	Other	unionists, community workers, members of non-government organizations and	Planned
	6th European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (June 19 - 21st 2023, Dublin)	Conferences	Research communities	Directed poster will be submitted.	Planned
	19th Annual Law and the Environment Conference at University College Cork (UCC)	Conferences	Research communities	20th April 2023.	Planned
ETH	N/A staff not yet recruited for Project - activity will be submitted in the next report				
REGIONH	Kick-off meeting for Real World Lab, Capital Region of Denmark	Education & training events	end user	Mapping of barriers and challenges in DRR/DRM and CCA	Planned (3rd of March 2022)
	Establish a communication forum between the researchers at DTU, project managers i	Meetings	Industry	Secure smooth contact between the project's partners and stakeholder in order to	Ongoing
	Yearly updates on DIRECTED's results for policy makers in REGIONH	Meetings	Regional authorities	Secure political support, maximise result's impact (especially related to governance	Planned (8th of February)
	One article in a professional journal/magazine/website (e.g. watertech).	Other scientific collaboration	Industry	Maximise result's impact	Planned
	'Awareness-building with stakeholders	Meetings	end user	Stakeholder engagement	Ongoing
ARSTPC-ER	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	National authorities	REMTECH - https://www.remtechexpo.com/	Planned
	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	National authorities	ECOMONDO https://www.ecomondo.com/	Planned
	Webinar	Education & training events	end user	Webinar or Real Game/Exercise with other Civil Protections Partners Territorial	Planned
	Meeting	Meetings	end user	2/3 meetings with RWL2 Stakeholders on Pilots Areas	Planned
	Collaboration with other EU funded project	Collaboration with EU Funded Proj	Research communities	STREAM PROJECT - Comacchio Test Site	
G&C	Awareness-building with stakeholders, potential clients & partners	Meetings	Industry	WP1.1 pilot area and stakeholder engagement	Planned
	RWL Stakeholder input gathering workshop	Education & training events	end user	WP1.1 pilot area and stakeholder engagement	Planned
	Information events in RWL (e.g. invite local authorities etc.)	Meetings	Local authorities		
	Tool demonstration (Future Danube Model)	Meetings	Industry		
	Contribution to related events and seminars (e.g. DRMKC, ICPDR events)	Conferences	Industry		
IASA	'Presentation during Youngs Summer Scientist Program to international PhD students.	Meetings	Research communities		Planned
	'Other scientific collaboration	Other scientific collaboration			
EV	'Awareness-building with stakeholders	Meetings	end user	WP1.1 pilot area and stakeholder engagement	
	RWL Stakeholder input gathering workshop	Education & training events	end user	WP1.1 pilot area and stakeholder engagement	
	'Information events in RWL	Meetings	Local authorities		
	DIRECTED meeting Cologne	Meetings	Other		
52°North	OGC Innovation Days, Disaster Resilience and Climate Workshop	Conferences	Research communities	together, two European project perspectives	Delivered
	EGU 2023 conference joint presentation (co-author)	Conferences	Research communities	of natural hazards	Planned
	Geospatial World Forum	Conferences	Other	government for better Climate Change Adaptation and Disaster Risk Reduction	Planned
	Open Earth Monitor Workshop	Conferences	Industry	Overview of Project goals and 52°North's architecture design	Planned
	IFGI Forum	Other scientific collaboration	Research communities	Overview of Project goals and 52°North's architecture design	Planned
ZSRT	Contacting stakeholders.	Meetings	business partners National authorities Regional authorities Local authorities Civil society	Contacting stakeholders, identifying the key players for the Real Word Lab. Prepari	Ongoing
ARPAE	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	National authorities	REMTECH - https://www.remtechexpo.com/	Planned
	Present DIRECTED project at conference	Conferences	National authorities	ECOMONDO https://www.ecomondo.com/	Planned
	Meeting	Meetings	end user	2/3 meetings with RWL2 Stakeholders on Pilots Areas	Planned
	Collaboration with other EU funded project	Collaboration with EU Funded Proj	Research communities	STREAM PROJECT - Comacchio Test Site	Ongoing

4.2 Year 1 – Communication Plan

Table 21: Communication plan - Year 1.

Name of Beneficiary	Communication Activity Name	Description	Target Audience	Communication Channel	Outcome	Status
Oasis Hub	Project Launch - press release	Write and publish press release relating to project launch	Citizens	Press Release	Linkedin - 2161 Impressions,	Delivered
	Project branding and website development	Website and Corporate Communications Assets developed	Citizens	Print materials	Preparation of Project commur	Delivered
	Create LinkedIn discussion group	Created LinkedIn discussion group to act as collaboration and dis	Civil Society	Social Media	Launched	Delivered
	Create YouTube Channel	Created YouTube Channel ready for new videos	Citizens	Social Media	Launched	Delivered
	Create Twitter account for Directed	Created Twitter account for Directed Communications	Citizens	Social Media	Launched	Delivered
	Create Mastodon account for Directed	Created Mastodon account for Directed Communications	Citizens	Social Media	Launched	Delivered
	Create Instagram account for Directed	Created Instagram account for Directed Communication	Citizens	Social Media	Launched	Delivered
	Biweekly social media posts on all channels	Regular information provided to followers on the Project progress	Citizens	Social Media	250 new users	Ongoing
	Videos - Introduction to Directed Project Video	Video - Introduction to Directed Project Video	Citizens	Social Media	100 viewers	Planned
	Development of Real World Lab brochures	Brochure used by Real World Labs to inform participants	Specific user communities	Print materials	400 readers	Planned
	Quarterly Blog	Blog on description of Project and call to action to join Linkedin G	Specific user communities	Newsletter	1000 readers	Ongoing
	TUBS	Project branding and website development	Website and Corporate Communications Assets developed	Citizens	Print materials	Preparation of Project commur
Social media posts on Twitter and Mastodon		Broad communications of DIRECTED Activity	Citizens	Social Media		Ongoing
GfZ	N/A staff not yet recruited for Project - activity will be submitted in the next report					
PIK	Contribute material for the project website	Information and images about the Danube RWL, e.g. photos and	Citizens	Media Article	improved DIRECTED Webpaç	Planned
DTU	Press release (with Region H)	Launch international Press Release with a Danish focus	Industry/business partners	Press Release	Visibility	Planned
	DIRECTED project web page at DTU	A website to communicate about DIRECTED in English as well a	Research communities	Social Media	Information sharing and visibili	Planned
GECO	News about the project Kick-Off	Description of project goals and GECO/SaferPlaces contribution	Civil Society	Social Media		Delivered
	Reposting Directed communications on social m	Communication updates about project activities	Industry/business partners	Social Media		Ongoing
RIFS	News about the ITA RWL	Challenges on DRR and CAA users involvement	Local authorities	Social Media		Planned
	Project page DIRECTED	Description of project on RIFS website https://www.rifs-potsdam.c	Research communities	Social Media		
SEI	Share news/posts from DIRECTED social media	Updates from the project	Research communities	Social Media		
	Cross-poste news/posts from DIRECTED social	We can leverage weADAPT to cross-post DIRECTED social mec	Research communities	Social Media		
UCC	Project page on DIRECTED	Description of project on MaREI website	Research communities	Social Media		Ongoing
	Share news/posts from DIRECTED social media	Updates from the project	Research communities	Social Media		Ongoing
REGIONH	Press release	Launch international Press Release together with DTU with a Da	Industry/business partners	Press Release	At least one media publish the	Planned
	Website on regionh.dk for DIRECTED	A website to communicate about DIRECTED's results in Danish	Industry/business partners	Social Media	At least 100 visitors	Planned
	One-pager in Danish about DIRECTED	Useable as a press kit for the stakeholders to use in their internal	Local authorities	Print materials	At least 100 one-pagers distrib	Planned
	SoMe from the kick-off meeting in the real world	SoMe posts at REGIONH's channels about the KOM	Industry/business partners	Social Media	at least 500	Planned
ARSTPC-ER	Share news and posts from DIRECTED's SoMe	The shared posts will be followed with short descriptions or transl	Industry/business partners	Social Media		Planned
	Press Releases	Description of the project goals and RWL	Civil Society	Media Article		Ongoing
G&C	page and link DIRECTED website on Agency w	Description of the project goals and RWL https://regioneer.it/gk34	Civil Society	Social Media		
	Newsletter	Description of the project goals and RWL	Civil Society	Newsletter		
	Quarterly blog on website	Status RWL Danube	Industry/business partners	Social Media		
G&C	Information stand during CISAR Symposium eve	Description of the project goals and RWL	Industry/business partners	Print materials		Planned
	Press Release Project Kick-off	Description of the project goals and RWL	Industry/business partners	Social Media		Delivered
	Re-posting of Directed social media communica	The overall project communications	Industry/business partners	Social Media		
IIASA	Special website on the IIASA platform	Description of the project goals and risk-layer framework	National authorities			Delivered
EV	Newsletter "Infofluss" for EV members	Description of the project goals and RWL in german	Industry/business partners	Print materials		
	Post on www.erfverband.de to inform about DIR	Description of the project goals and RWL in german	Civil Society	Press Release		
52°North	OnePager about DIRECTED in german to inform	Description of the project goals and RWL in german	Industry/business partners	Newsletter		
	Project Press Release Project Kick-off	Description of project goals including focus on 52°North activities	Civil Society	Social Media		Delivered
	Re-posting of Directed social media communica	The overall project communications	Industry/business partners	Social Media		Ongoing
ZSRT	2 pager about DIRECTED as part of Annual Rep	Description of project goals including focus on 52°North activities	Industry/business partners	Print materials		Planned
	1 pager about DIRECTED as project refence on	Description of project goals including focus on 52°North activities	Industry/business partners	Social Media		Planned
ARPAE	Project communication at local level.	Sending information on the project to partners and potential RWL	Local authorities	Interview		Planned
	page and link DIRECTED website on Allertamet	Description of the project goals and RWL	Specific user communities	Social Media		Planned
ARPAE	page and link DIRECTED website on Agency w	Description of the project goals and RWL	Civil Society	Media Article		Planned
	page and link DIRECTED website on Agency w	Description of the project goals and RWL	Civil Society	Media Article		Planned

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Partners

